

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

 OPEN ACCESS

Received: 09-05-2022

Accepted: 31-07-2022

Published: 07-09-2022

Citation: Vidya KM, Manoharan AN (2022) Morphometric Analysis for Sustainable Development of Watersheds Using Multisensor Satellite Data: A Case Study from Shiriya River Basin. Indian Journal of Science and Technology 15(35): 1691-1702. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v15i35.994>

* **Corresponding author.**vidyakm2304@gmail.com

Funding: Authors wish to gratefully acknowledge the Kerala State Council for Science, Technology, and the Environment (KSCSTE) for the financial support

Competing Interests: None

Copyright: © 2022 Vidya & Manoharan. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Published By Indian Society for Education and Environment ([iSee](https://www.indjst.org/))

ISSN

Print: 0974-6846

Electronic: 0974-5645

Morphometric Analysis for Sustainable Development of Watersheds Using Multisensor Satellite Data: A Case Study from Shiriya River Basin

K M Vidya^{1*}, A N Manoharan¹

¹ Department of Post-Graduate Studies and Research in Geology, Government College Kasaragod, (affiliated to Kannur University), Kerala, Vidyanagar, Kasaragod, India

Abstract

Objectives: The goal of this research is to calculate, compare and analyze the morphometric drainage parameters of Shiriya River Basin (SRB), Kasaragod, Kerala, using DEMs acquired by different satellite sensors and topographic data (SOI toposheet) for sustainable watershed development. **Methods:** The Arc GIS 10.3.1 software was used to measure linear, relief, and areal aspects of morphometry. The input data used for deriving the drainage network of the SRB were SOI toposheet (1:50000 scale), SRTM DEM (90m), Cartosat, ASTER and ALOS PALSAR DEM of resolution 30 m each. The relative error percentage of basic parameters derived from DEMs concerning the toposheet is calculated. A groundwater potential map is prepared using weighted overlay analysis of thematic layers (geology, geomorphology, slope, drainage density, lineament density and depth to water level). **Findings:** Present study revealed that the parameters derived from SRTM DEM data are more similar to those derived from toposheet. Most of the parameters obtained from each input DEM are more or less equal, and the minor variation may be due to varied data collecting and processing methodologies used for DEM creation. SRB is characterized by 6 th order stream with a dendritic drainage pattern, which is elongated and less susceptible to soil erosion. SRB has an intermediate texture and is in a mature stage of geomorphic evolution. Inference from the ground water potential zonation map indicates that major portion of the SRB has moderate ground water potential. **Application/improvement:** The study would be a valuable source for identifying water recharge sites, basin modelling, and groundwater prospect mapping. **Novelty:** This research has attempted to compare and analyze the morphometric parameters' results from multisensor satellite data for sustainable watershed management. An attempt has been done to understand the relation between morphometric parameters and ground water potential of SRB using Groundwater potential zonation map.

Keywords: Drainage morphometry; Shiriya River basin; GIS; Karnataka; Kerala

1 Introduction

”The measuring and mathematical study of the shape of the earth’s surface and the extents of its landforms is known as morphometry”⁽¹⁾. Morphometric analysis has received much interest recently because of its application in different aspects like watershed delineation, Runoff modelling, soil erosion and flood susceptibility, groundwater map generation, natural resources management, and conservation⁽²⁾. In basin studies, numerous methodologies and techniques can be used to extract the Basin boundaries and drainage networks. While some researchers select traditional methods like topographical maps and field surveys to support their studies, others favour current approaches like GIS-produced digital elevation models (DEMs), digital surface models (DSMs), and remote-sensing techniques.

Several studies on morphometric analysis have been carried out in numerous basins of Kerala. Morphometric analysis of the Ithikkara river basin is studied using SRTM DEM by⁽³⁾ using Basin-wise DEM-based Automated Morphometry (BaDAM) toolbox. Another study has been carried out in Kerala to identify the role of morphometric parameters in controlling the runoff efficiency of the Valakkayi Tode watershed of the Valapattanam River⁽⁴⁾. Neotectonic evidence linked with the Achankovil shear zone is studied with the help of morphometric analysis and field investigations⁽⁵⁾. But the comparison of morphometric characteristics derived from two or more DEM datasets has only been made recently in Kerala in a few research.

There is a great demand for studying and assessing a drainage basin’s physiographic features and hydrologic behaviour by utilizing geospatial datasets from various DEMs in recent years. As a result, there is a significant question about the accuracy and sensitivity of these datasets derived from various DEMs. The current study compares drainage features of the SRB derived from four different DEMs: ASTER 30 m, SRTM 90 m, CARTOSAT 30 m, and ALOS 30 m and Survey of India toposheet 1: 50000. and also calculate relative error percentages of DEM-derived morphometric parameters with toposheet. For the effective management of water resources of a basin, it is very crucial to know the water availability of that Basin. Hence groundwater potential zonation map was also created using the weighted overlay analysis. The reason for choosing this study location is that SRB is one of the minor river basins of the Kasaragod district, which has received less attention from other researchers. No literature regarding morphometry is available for reference in the SRB. So, it could be a primary guide for further study in the area to evaluate and manage the Basin’s natural resources.

1.1 Study Area

SRB is one of the minor river basins of Northern Kerala. It is geographically located between latitudes $12^{\circ}31'41.26''$ N - $12^{\circ}45'15.98''$ N and longitude $74^{\circ}55'26.73''$ E - $75^{\circ}20'55.74''$ E (Figure 1). The river’s total length is about 65 km, 38 kilometers in the Kasaragod district of Kerala, and the remaining part is in the Dakshina Kannada district of Karnataka State. The river rises from the Anne Gundi Hills from the height of 270 m from the Mean Sea Level and joins the Kumbala backwaters. It finally empties into the Arabian sea. The total basin area of the river is 630 square kilometers; out of it, 290 square kilometers are in Kerala.

Fig 1. Study area’s location map.

1.1.1 Geology

The major portion is enclosed by laterite overlying the peninsular gneiss in the study area. The laterite is a result of weathering of charnockite /Hornblende biotite gneiss. Small patches of syenite, dolerite, and recent tertiary/quarternary alluvial deposits like grit, sandstone, and clay with lignite intercalations are seen as part of the Warkalli formation at the mouth side of the river basin. Basic dykes are also present on the southeastern side of the study area. Some garnitiferous sillimanite gneiss/schist patches are located at the NW- SE side of the Basin. Granite intrusion is present on the southern side of the Basin. Patches of hornblende diopside granulite schist rocks are seen almost in the middle portion of the SRB.It has some lineaments, with NW-SE’s primary trend (Figure 2).

Fig 2. Study area’s geology map.

2 Methodology

Morphometric analysis was carried out in this study using toposheet and GIS methodologies (Figure 3). The toposheets of the 1:50000 scale corresponding to the SRB were downloaded from the Nakshe portal (website) of the Survey of India (SOI). As a first step, georeferencing and the digitization of streams from the toposheets were done in Arc GIS 10.3.1 software. Each stream was digitized as a line feature with a unique Id and stream number. The method proposed by Strahler⁽⁶⁾ is used to order the streams. The relief aspect of the Basin was assessed using contour values. The length of the digitized stream was calculated using Arc GIS 10.3.1 geometry calculation tool, and the attribute table was exported to Microsoft Excel for further calculations of morphometric parameters.

Initially, morphometric parameters are calculated from the toposheet. After that, digital elevation models were downloaded from Earth explorer (SRTM 90 m and ASTER 30 m), the Earth data portal of NASA (ALOS PALSAR 30 m) and the BHUVAN (CARTOSAT 30 m) web portal of ISRO, respectively (Table 1). Then, for a better comparison of morphometric parameters, each of the DEMs was resampled to the same resolution. Then, using the fill option of spatial analyst extension of the hydrology tool, all the four DEMs mentioned above were pre-processed to seal the voids. Then, each DEM was re-projected into Universal Transverse Mercator (zone 43N) projection for further analysis.

Table 1. Data sources used for the present study

Data	Resolution	Source
Toposheet	1:50000 scale	Nakshe portal of SOI
ALOS PALSAR DEM	30m	Earth data portal of NASA
SRTM DEM	90m	USGS earth explorer
CARTOSAT DEM	30m	Bhuvan web portal of ISRO
ASTER DEM	30m	USGS earth explorer

Fig 3. Methodology flow chart.

For generating a stream network from any DEM, specific steps must be followed in Arc GIS software. The initial step is finding the flow direction corresponding to individual cells. The next step is to determine the accumulated number of cells upstream, denoting watershed derived from fill DEM. The selection of threshold values is essential. Because of drainage density and stream frequency change with a threshold value. Then, stream identification was made based on the cells with a higher accumulation value than the threshold value. Stream order was measured using the hydrology option after generating streams using a typical threshold value for different DEMs (SRTM, ASTER, ALOS PALSAR and Cartosat). Finally, the generated stream was converted into a vector for further calculation with the help of the stream to feature option in the hydrology tool.

The drainage layer calculates fundamental aspects like the number and length of streams, area, perimeter and length of the Basin. Then, the remaining parameters of morphometry were calculated with the help of formulas (Table 2) in Microsoft excel.

Table 2. Morphometric parameters

Morphometric Parameters	Formula	
Stream order (u)	Hierarchical rank	Strahler ⁽⁶⁾
Stream length (Lu)	Total Length of Stream	Horton ⁽⁷⁾
Mean stream length (Lsm)	$Lsm = Lu \div Nu$	Horton, ⁽⁷⁾
Stream length ratio (RL)	$RL = Lu \div (Lu - 1)$	Horton ⁽⁷⁾
Bifurcation ratio (Rb)	$Rb = Nu \div (Nu + 1)$	Schumm ⁽⁸⁾
Rho coefficient (ρ)	$\rho = RL \div Rb$	Horton ⁽⁷⁾
Relief	Relief ratio (Rh)	$Rh = Bh \div Lb$ Schumm ⁽⁸⁾

Continued on next page

Table 2 continued

Areal	Ruggedness number (Rn)	$Rn = Bh \times Dd$	Strahler ⁽⁹⁾
	Drainage density (Dd)	$Dd = L \div A$	Horton ⁽⁷⁾
	Stream frequency (Fs)	$Fs = N \div A$	Horton ⁽⁷⁾
	Drainage texture (T)	$T = Dd \times Fs$	Smith ⁽¹⁰⁾
	Form factor (Ff)	$Ff = A \div Lb^2$	Horton ⁽⁷⁾
	Circulatory ratio (Rc)	$Rc = 4 \times \pi A / P^2$	Miller ⁽¹¹⁾
	Elongation ratio (Re)	$Re = \sqrt[1.128]{A / Lb}$	Schumm ⁽⁸⁾
	Length of overland flow (Lg)	$Lg = 1 \div (2Dd)$	Horton ⁽⁷⁾

Here Nu denotes total number of stream segments of order u, Nu+1 is used for number of stream segments of next higher order, Lu-1 corresponds to length of stream segments of previous lower order, Lb, A and P is used for length, area and perimeter of the basin, value of π is 3.14

After calculating all the parameters of morphometry relative error percentage of basic parameters with respect to the toposheet was assessed. To manage the water resources of SRB, it is crucial to know water availability. Hence the groundwater potential map is generated using weightage overlay analysis in Arc GIS 10.3.1 software using different thematic layers (geology, geomorphology, drainage density, slope, lineament density and water level). The critical aspects of these thematic maps are described below. The ranks and weightages of parameters assigned for various classes of different layers are given in Table 3. The weightage and rank are given to a factor based on their influence rate on groundwater occurrence. The highest weightage is assigned for the factor that dominantly influences the groundwater occurrence and vice versa.

Table 3. Ranks and weightages of parameters assigned for various classes of different layers.

Theme	Source	Weight	Identified factors	Rank	Ground potential	water	Overall weightage
Geomorphology	Toposheet SOI,1:50000	6	Denudational hills, Lower plateau	2	Poor		12
			Flood Plain, Valley, Islands	5	Very good		15
			Young coastal plain	4	Good		24
Lineament density (km/sq.km)	Bhukosh web portal	5	0-0.64	1	Very Poor		5
			0.65-1.3	3	Moderate		15
			1.4-1.9	4	Good		20
			2-2.5	5	Very good		25
Slope (Degree)	Prepared from SRTM DEM	3	0-5.38	5	Very good		15
			5.38-10.75	4	Good		12
			10.76-16.13	3	Moderate		9
Geology	Toposheet SOI,1:50000	4	16.14-21.5	2	Poor		6
			Laterite, Grit, Sandstone with clay intercalations	5	Very good		20
			Dolerite, Granite, Amphibolite, Basic dyke, Syenite	1	Very Poor		4
			Garnitiferous sillimanite gneiss/schist, Hornblende diopside granulite schist	2	Poor		8
Drainage density (km/sq.km)	Prepared from SRTM DEM	2	Biotite gneiss/Hornblende biotite gneiss	3	Moderate		12
			1.13-1.87	4	Good		8
			1.87-2.60	3	Moderate		6
			2.60-3.33	2	Poor		4
Depth to water level (m)	Collected from district ground water department, Kasaragod and Mangalore	1	3.33-4.07	1	Very poor		2
			4.66-8.58	4	Good		4
			8.58-12.49	3	Moderate		3
			12.49-16.4	2	Poor		2
			16.4-20.32	1	Very poor		1

3 Results

The outcome of the drainage basin analysis of the Shiriya river is discussed below.

3.1 Stream Order (u)

The present study revealed that the Shiriya river is a sixth-order stream with a chiefly dendritic drainage pattern (Figure 4) in which tributaries join the main stream in many directions resembling tree branches. This drainage pattern is typical in homogeneous terrain.

Fig 4. Drainage network map derived from ALOS PALSAR, ASTER, CARTO, SAT, SRTM, and Toposheet (SOI) DEMs.

3.2 Stream Number (Nu)

The total number of streams obtained from toposheet, PALSAR, SRTM, CARTO and ASTER DEM are 1759, 1723, 1730, 1722 and 1807, respectively (Table 4). Slight variation in a number of streams derived from different sources may be due to spatial change of elevation, vertical accuracy and raster grid size of the digital elevation model.

3.2 Stream Length (Lu)

Stream length and number of streams are directly proportional. A shorter stream indicates that the area has greater slopes and finer textures. Conversely, larger streams are characterized by flat or nearly flat areas⁽¹²⁾. The total length of streams derived from toposheet, PALSAR, SRTM, Cartosat and ASTER DEMs is 1289.53km.,1184.2km.,1118.86km.,1172.44km., and 1267.24km, respectively (Table 4).

Table 4. Linear parameters of SRB

Parameter	Toposheet	PALSAR	SRTM	Carto sat	ASTER
Basin area A (Sq. km)	620	623	614	614	634
Perimeter P (km)	157	176	145	175	176
Basin length Lb (km)	43.98	45.1	44.17	44.43	41.31
stream order (u)	Stream Number (Nu)				
1	1305	1338	1340	1327	1372
2	351	292	300	289	322
3	75	68	65	74	85
4	21	19	19	25	21
5	6	5	5	6	6

Continued on next page

Table 4 continued

6	1	1	1	1	1
Total	1759	1723	1730	1722	1807
	Stream Length (Lu) (km)				
1	726.95	614.54	579.01	617.52	655.89
2	250.51	263.2	251.15	243.27	290.82
3	126.6	155.8	143.3	155.1	170.4
4	82.44	64.06	62.87	77.92	72.31
5	58.37	45.42	46.05	40.99	39.65
6	44.66	41.14	36.81	37.62	38.21
Total	1289.53	1184.2	1118.86	1172.44	1267.24
Mean stream length (Lsm)	0.73	0.69	0.65	0.69	0.7
	Stream Length Ratio (RL)				
2nd/1st	0.34	0.43	0.43	0.39	0.44
3 rd/2nd	0.5	0.59	0.57	0.64	0.58
4th/3rd	0.65	0.41	0.44	0.5	0.42
5th/4th	0.71	0.71	0.73	0.53	0.54
5 th/6th	0.76	0.9	0.79	0.92	0.96
Mean stream length Ratio	0.59	0.61	0.59	0.59	0.59
	Bifurcation Ratio (Rb)				
1st/2nd	3.72	4.58	4.47	4.59	4.26
2nd/3rd	4.68	4.29	4.61	3.9	3.79
3rd/4th	3.57	3.58	3.42	2.96	4.05
4th/5th	3.5	3.8	3.8	4.17	3.5
5th/6th	6	5	5	6	6
Mean Bifurcation	4.29	4.25	4.26	4.32	4.32
Rho coefficient (ρ)	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14

3.4 Mean Stream Length (Lsm)

It is the ratio between the overall length of a stream of a particular order (Lu) and the stream number (Nu) for that order. Lsm is a distinctive property of drainage networks and their components. Table 4 shows the average mean stream length derived from different sources.

3.5 Stream Length Ratio (RL)

RL is the same for streams of all orders within a watershed. Any deviations from the constant value of the RL can be traced to differences in slope and topographical conditions⁽¹³⁾. Table 4 displays the RL values of the SRB.

3.6 Bifurcation Ratio (Rb)

The geology and lithology control the Rb of a basin. Usually, it falls between 3.0 to 5.0. The watershed that had undergone less structural disturbance has lower values of Rb (less than 3), and the one that had undergone high structural disturbance has higher Rb values^(6,14). Mean Rb values obtained from toposheet, PALSAR, SRTM, CARTO, and ASTER DEMs are 4.29, 4.25, 4.26, 4.32, and 4.32, respectively (Table 4). Mean Rb derived from CARTOSAT, ASTER is equal. These values indicate the elongated nature of the SRB, where geologic structures present in the Basin has a moderate impact on the drainage network development.

3.7 Rho Coefficient (ρ)

The Rho values of the study area calculated from different sources (toposheet, PALSAR, SRTM, Cartosat and ASTER DEM) are similar (0.14). This value indicates that the SRB has less storage capacity during a flood.

3.8 Relief (H)

H of the SRB obtained from SRTM DEM is 0.38 km, ASTER DEM has 0.39 km, PALSAR DEM shows 0.37 km, Cartosat DEM has 0.23km and 0.37 km from toposheet (Table 5).

3.9 Relief Ratio (Rh)

Rh depends upon the slope and geology of the Basin. Higher values of Rh link to the hilly region of the Basin, whereas lower values indicate the plain region. The Basin's relief ratio was obtained from toposheet-0.008, SRTM-0.009, PALSAR-0.008, Cartosat-0.005 and ASTER DEM-0.009 (Table 5).

Table 5. Relief and areal parameters of SRB, Kasaragod, Kerala.

Morphometric parameters	Toposheet	PALSAR	SRTM	CARTO	ASTER
Total relief (H) (km)	0.37	0.44	0.35	0.33	0.39
Relief ratio (Rh)	0.008	0.008	0.009	0.005	0.009
Ruggedness number (Rn)	0.82	0.70	0.69	0.44	0.78
Drainage density (Dd) (kms/km ²)	2.23	1.9	1.82	1.91	1.99
Stream frequency (Fs)	2.84	2.76	2.82	2.8	2.85
Drainage texture (Rt)	6.33	5.24	5.13	5.35	5.67
Form factor (Rf)	0.32	0.31	0.31	0.31	0.37
Circularity ratio (Rc)	0.31	0.25	0.37	0.25	0.25
Elongation ratio (Re)	0.60	0.62	0.63	0.63	0.68
Length of overland flow (Lg)	0.22	0.26	0.27	0.26	0.25

3.10 Ruggedness Number (Rn)

The ruggedness number of the SRB derived from the different DEMs shows slight variation. The obtained values are 0.82, 0.70, 0.69, 0.44, 0.78 for toposheet, PALSAR, SRTM, CARTO, ASTER DEMS respectively. These results show that the region is less vulnerable to soil erosion.

3.11 Drainage Density (Dd)

Dd is an indirect indicator of groundwater potential associated with surface overflow and permeability. The region with high surface runoff will have a higher drainage density; thus, infiltration will be lower. Dd of the SRB is 2.23 km/km² (Toposheet), 1.9 km/km² (ALOS PALSAR), 1.82 km/km² (SRTM), 1.91 km/km² (Cartosat) and 1.99 km/km² (ASTER). Drainage density less than 2 is grouped as low, 2-4 as moderate, 4-6 as high and greater than 6 is treated as very high drainage density⁽¹⁵⁾. SRB belongs to a low to moderate drainage density category, which infers the presence of permeable subsoil with good vegetation cover⁽¹⁶⁾.

3.12 Stream Frequency (Fs)

The lithology, as well as texture, influences it. The Fs for the Basin derived from different sources (Toposheet, PALSAR, SRTM, Cartosat and ASTER DEM) are 2.84, 2.76, 2.82, 2.80 and 2.85 individually. The low Fs values of the SRB may be credited to moderate infiltration capacity and small relief.

3.13 Drainage Texture (T)

T is controlled by the region's base rock, relief, and infiltration capability. Smith⁽¹⁰⁾ divided drainage texture into five groups that are very coarse when the T is less than 2, coarse when T is between 2 and 4, moderate when the texture ranges from 4 - 6, fine when the texture ranges from 6 - 8, and very fine when it is greater than 8. Drainage texture of the watershed derived from Toposheet -6.33, PALSAR- 5.24, SRTM -5.13, CARTOSAT- 5.35 and ASTER DEM -5.67. It indicates that the Basin belongs to a moderate to fine drainage texture category.

3.14 Form Factor (Ff)

An exactly circular basin has an Ff value of 0.7854. For elongated basins, Ff values will be smaller, and it experiences longer duration flows with lower peaks. The higher value of the Ff indicates shorter duration flows of the more prominent peak. The Ff of the study area varies around 0.32 (Toposheet) and 0.31 (PALSAR, SRTM and Cartosat DEM). ASTER DEM shows a slightly higher value (0.37). This result specifies the elongated nature of the SRB with a smaller peak flow that lasts longer.

3.15 Circularity Ratio (Rc)

Range⁽¹¹⁾ of Rc is 0.4 to 0.5. The Rc value of the SRB is tabulated in Table 5, which shows the Basin as elongated and made of permeable homogenous geologic materials.

3.16 Elongation Ratio (Re)

Re fluctuates from 0.6 to 1.0 along with the climate and geology of the region. Using the elongation ratio, it is possible to classify watersheds as most elongated if the value is less than 0.5, elongated when the value is between 0.5 and 0.7, least elongated if Re is 0.7-0.8, oval when Re is 0.8-0.9 and circular if the value is between 0.9 and 1.0. The studied Basin has a range of Re value (0.60 to 0.68), indicating that the SRB is elongated (Table 5).

3.17 Length of overland flow (Lg)

Lg impacts the hydrologic and physiographic evolution of a watershed. Lg of the Shiriya river basin obtained from toposheet, PALSAR, SRTM, Cartosat, and ASTER DEMs are 0.22, 0.26, 0.27, 0.26 and 0.25, respectively. It shows that the SRB has a gentle slope that is less susceptible to erosion and is in a mature stage of geomorphic evolution.

3.18 Ground water potential zonation map

Ground water potential map of SRB is shown in Figure 5. The area is classified into 5 zones based on ground water availability as very poor, poor, moderate, high and very high. Factors that facilitates the infiltration rate of the regions are characterised by valleys, low drainage density, high lineament density and low slope. Those regions characterised by these factors are the very high potential zone of the ground water.

Fig 5. Ground water potential zones of SRB.

4 Discussion

The significant findings of the study are discussed below. The Basin is characterized by 6th order stream with a dendritic drainage pattern, which is elongated and less susceptible to soil erosion. The SRB has an intermediate texture and permeable homogenous geologic materials. The Basin has a gentle slope that is less susceptible to erosion and is in a mature stage of geomorphic evolution.

Many studies have been conducted in various basins regarding morphometric analysis from various data sources^(17–19). While comparing the results of parameters derived from different sources of DEMs with that of toposheet, in some of the research⁽¹⁸⁾, it is observed that morphometric parameters derived from SRTM DEM data match with the toposheet and are suitable for drainage basin analysis. But in some research, when considering the vegetation cover along with different data sets, Basin with high vegetation, a morphometric parameter derived from SRTM DEM matches with that of toposheet and Basin with Low vegetation cover, parameters derived from ALOS DEM are more similar to that of toposheet⁽¹⁹⁾.

This study also revealed that parameters derived from SRTM DEM match with the toposheet. Different DEMs used in the present study are more or less matched with the toposheet. Minor variation in drainage networks results because the flow direction grid is the primary determinant of drainage network derivation from DEMs. Variations in elevation and spatial resolution of the data may also impact the resultant networks.

To compare the five sets of data relative error percentage relative to the toposheet is calculated (Figure 6). Relative error percentage is the percentage of the difference between parameters derived from toposheet (X_{REF}) and corresponding parameters (X_{DEM}) derived from DEMs⁽²⁰⁾. Here sign of the value is not considered. Additionally, morphometric attributes derived from the DEM were standardized to TOPO to understand the variability of distinct morphometric attributes (Figure 7).

Fig 6. Relative error percentage of basic morphometric parameters

Fig 7. Morphometric attributes standardized to TOPO

Figure 6 clearly shows that among the basic parameters, the relative error percentage in the L2, L3, L5, perimeter and basin length is less in SRTM DEM data than in the other DEMs used in the study. Stream length shows relatively higher error in most data sets than stream numbers of individual streams. Among stream numbers, 5th order shows significantly less error from reference data (toposheet). There is no relative error since the number of sixth-order streams is equal in all data sets. Among various parameters defining basin size (Area, Perimeter and Basin length), Perimeter displays a more significant error due to the irregularities of the basin boundary. From Figure 6, it is clear that SRTM DEM data shows a relatively less error percentage, and PALSAR DEM shows a higher error percentage than other sets of DEMs. Due to varied data collecting and processing methodologies for DEM creation, DEMs with equal spatial resolution can have distinct morphometry derivatives⁽²¹⁾.

The SRB ground water potential zonation map is designed to the analysis of water resources of the region. It is evident from the map that there is a considerable water potential in the area of the basin where lineament density is high and drainage density is low. The spatial distribution map of depth to water level confirms it as well. Low depth to water level is seen in regions with high lineament density and vice versa. Average of ten years depth to waterlevel is considered in the present study.

5 Conclusion

This study aims to compare the morphometric parameters of the SRB based on the DEM type. This is an indirect method of determining the relative vertical accuracy of DEMs. Due to varied data collecting and processing methodologies for DEM creation, DEMs with identical spatial resolution can have distinct morphometric derivatives, which is understood from the study. The present investigation proposes that morphometric parameters (L2, L3, L5, Perimeter and Basin length) can be efficiently retrieved from SRTM DEM. The study concluded that the value of parameters derived from SRTM data is almost equal to that of parameters derived from the toposheet. SRTM DEM shows less relative error percentage with respect to toposheet. Hence, SRTM DEM data can be considered more suitable for the Shiriya River Basin morphometric analysis than other open-source DEMs employed in the present study. The SRB is morphometrically identified as sixth order, with a dendritic stream pattern. It is common in homogeneous terrain. Some structural or tectonic control in the SRB is clearly understood by the presence of lineaments and structural discontinuity. Elevation from different DEMs of the SRB indicates that it has low to moderate relief; as a result, there isn't much surface runoff. The Rn values of the SRB are 0.82, 0.70, 0.69, 0.44 and 0.78 for toposheet, PALSAR, SRTM, CARTO and ASTER DEMs respectively. The Rn values indicate the Basin's little runoff and high infiltration capacity. Dd of the SRB is 2.23 km/km² (Toposheet), 1.9 km/km² (ALOS PALSAR), 1.82 km/km² (SRTM), 1.91 km/km² (Cartosat) and 1.99 km/km² (ASTER). Drainage texture (T) of the watershed derived from Toposheet -6.33, PALSAR-5.24, SRTM -5.13, CARTOSAT- 5.35 and ASTER DEM -5.67 are individually. The studied Basin has a Circularity ratio (Re) (0.60 to 0.68). All three parameters (Dd, T, Re) specify that the SRB is elongated with intermediate texture and permeable homogenous geologic materials. Hence the Basin has moderate infiltration capability, which has moderate groundwater potential. This result is also supported by the ground water potential zonation map. The output of the study can be very well used for the sustainable development of the SRB. Since no studies were available on the morphometry of the SRB, this work could be a primary guide for further study in the area.

Acknowledgements

Authors wish to gratefully acknowledge the Kerala State Council for Science, Technology, and the Environment (KSCSTE) for the financial support. The first writer also thankful for the Director, Research, Kannur University and the Principal, Government college Kasaragod and The HOD and research supervisor Department of Geology and research centre Government College Kasaragod.

References

- 1) Esin AI, Akgul M, Akay AO, Yurtseven H. Comparison of LiDAR-based morphometric analysis of a drainage basin with results obtained from UAV, TOPO, ASTER and SRTM-based DEMs. *Arabian Journal of Geosciences*. 2021;14(5):1–5. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12517-021-06705-3>.
- 2) Kasi V, Pinninti R, Landa SR, Rathinasamy M, Sangamreddi C, Kuppli RR, et al. Comparison of different digital elevation models for drainage morphometric parameters: a case study from South India. *Arabian Journal of Geosciences*. 2020;13(19):1–7. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12517-020-06049-4>.
- 3) Jose C, Thomas J, Prasannakumar V, Reghunath R. BaDAM Toolbox: A GIS-Based Approach for Automated Drainage Basin Morphometry. *Journal of the Indian Society of Remote Sensing*. 2019;47(3):467–478. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12524-018-0913-9>.
- 4) Akhil R, Prasad TK, Vineethkumar V. Analyzing the significance of morphometric parameters in runoff efficiency: a case study in Valakkayi Tode tropical watershed, Valapattanam River, Kerala, India. *Journal of Sedimentary Environments*. 2022;7(1):67–78. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43217-021-00083-2>.

- 5) Praseeda E, Ganapathy GP. Neotectonic evidences associated with Achankovil shear zone using morphometric analysis and field investigations. *Modeling Earth Systems and Environment*. 2020;6(3):1487–1508. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40808-020-00765-2>.
- 6) Strahler AN. Quantitative geomorphology of drainage basins and channel networks. New York, McGraw-Hill book. 1964.
- 7) Horton RE. Erosional development of streams and their drainage density: Hydrophysical approach to quantitative geomorphology. *Bulletin of the Geological Society of America*. 1945;5:275–370. Available from: [https://doi.org/10.1130/0016-7606\(1945\)56\[275:EDOSAT\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1130/0016-7606(1945)56[275:EDOSAT]2.0.CO;2).
- 8) Schumm SA. Evolution of drainage systems and slopes in Badlands at Perth Amboy, New Jersey. *Bulletin of the Geological Society of America*. 1956;67:597–646. Available from: [https://doi.org/10.1130/0016-7606\(1956\)67\[597:EODSAS\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1130/0016-7606(1956)67[597:EODSAS]2.0.CO;2).
- 9) Strahler AN. DIMENSIONAL ANALYSIS APPLIED TO FLUVIALLY ERODED LANDFORMS. *Geological Society of America Bulletin*. 1958;69(3):279–279.
- 10) Smith KG. Standards for grading texture of erosional topography. *American Journal of Science*. 1950;248(9):655–668. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.2475/ajs.248.9.655>.
- 11) Miller VC. A quantitative geomorphic study of drainage basin characteristics in the Clinch Mountain area, Virginia and Tennessee, Project NR 389-042. New York. 1953.
- 12) Prakash K, Rawat D, Singh S, Chaubey K, Kanhaiya S, Mohanty T. Morphometric analysis using SRTM and GIS in synergy with depiction: a case study of the Karmanasa River basin, North central India. *Applied Water Science*. 2019;9(1). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13201-018-0887-3>.
- 13) Rajasekhar M, Raju GS, Raju RS. Morphometric analysis of the Jilledubanderu river basin, Anantapur District, Andhra Pradesh, India, using geospatial technologies. *Groundwater for Sustainable Development*;vol. 11. Anantapur District, Andhra Pradesh, India. 2020. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gsd.2020.100434>.
- 14) Singh AP, Arya AK, Singh DS. Morphometric Analysis of Ghaghara River Basin, India, Using SRTM Data and GIS. *Journal of the Geological Society of India*. 2020;95(2):169–178. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12594-020-1406-3>.
- 15) Kudnar NS, Rajasekhar M. A study of the morphometric analysis and cycle of erosion in Wainganga Basin, India. *Modeling Earth Systems and Environment*. 2020;6(1):311–327. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40808-019-00680-1>.
- 16) Adewole AO, Ike F, Eludoyin AO. A multi-sensor-based evaluation of the morphometric characteristics of Opa river basin in Southwest Nigeria. *International Journal of Image and Data Fusion*. 2020;11(2):185–200. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/19479832.2019.1683622>.
- 17) Shaikh M, Yadav S, Manekar V. Accuracy Assessment of Different Open-Source Digital Elevation Model Through Morphometric Analysis for a Semi-arid River Basin in the Western Part of India. *Journal of Geovisualization and Spatial Analysis*. 2021;5(2):1–21. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41651-021-00089-4>.
- 18) Niyazi B, Zaidi S, Masoud M. Comparative Study of Different Types of Digital Elevation Models on the Basis of Drainage Morphometric Parameters (Case Study of Wadi Fatimah Basin, KSA). *Earth Systems and Environment*. 2019;3(3):539–550. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41748-019-00111-2>.
- 19) Karabulut MS, Özdemir H. Comparison of basin morphometry analyses derived from different DEMs on two drainage basins in Turkey. *Environmental Earth Sciences*. 2019;78(18):1–4. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12665-019-8585-5>.
- 20) Thomas J, Prasannakumar V. Comparison of basin morphometry derived from topographic maps, ASTER and SRTM DEMs: an example from Kerala, India. *Geocarto International*. 2015;30(3):346–364. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10106049.2014.955063>.
- 21) Jain AO, Thaker TP, Misra AK, Singh AK, Kumari P. Determination of sensitivity of drainage morphometry towards hydrological response interactions for various datasets. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*. 2021;23(2):1799–1822. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-020-00652-x>.